

D7.2 Plan for Dissemination and Communication Activities

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Introduction

The REMEDY project proposes a game-changing technology in the form of an *archibiome tattoo* – a living, functional, and customizable microbial surface capable of transforming how buildings look, function, and interact with their environment.

The project aims to achieve a breakthrough in fundamental research in microbiology and synthetic biology, transfer the know-how to materials science in the form of engineered living materials, and develop compatible biofabrication processes that allow personalised design in the architectural context.

Since REMEDY seeks innovative and interdisciplinary solutions, an effective dissemination and communication strategy is essential to ensure that the project's advances reach a wide range of stakeholders, including the scientific community, industry partners, policymakers, and the general public.

This document outlines how REMEDY will communicate its objectives, progress, and results with the identified target audiences, foster cross-disciplinary collaboration, and support the societal acceptance of microbial technologies in architecture. By employing a range of communication channels and activities, this plan aims to raise awareness, engage key audiences, and promote the adoption of microorganisms as essential allies for healthier, more sustainable, and more adaptive built environments.

Communication objectives

The communication objectives of REMEDY project are designed to support the overall goal of achieving a breakthrough in fundamental research in microbiology and synthetic biology, transferring the know-how to materials science through engineered living materials, and develop compatible biofabrication processes that enable personalised design in architectural contexts, by ensuring that the project's vision, activities, and outcomes are clearly and effectively conveyed to relevant audiences.

To support the success of the project and meet the set objectives and key results, several communication activities are planned. By clearly defining communication intentions, we can ensure that messages resonate with target audiences and promote the project's goals. The following objectives have been established to guide communication efforts and maximize the impact of our activities.

- **Objective 1 (O1):** Raise awareness of REMEDY and improve understanding of living microbial materials.
- **Objective 2 (O2):** Showcase REMEDY's scientific innovation and technical breakthroughs.
- **Objective 3 (O3):** Highlight the environmental and functional benefits of living inks developed in REMEDY.
- **Objective 4 (O4):** Promote REMEDY's new product (living ink) and a new 'disruptive technology' as a transformative tool for architecture, with potential to enhance well-being, aesthetic experience, and ecological harmony in the built environment.
- **Objective 5 (O5):** Engage stakeholders with REMEDY's results and activities.
- **Objective 6 (O6):** Ensure wide dissemination of the project's best practices and build a strong position of REMEDY in the field of probiotic architecture by promoting its societal benefits and active participation in cross-sector innovation ecosystems.

Target audience

To effectively implement the communication objectives outlined above, it is crucial to tailor activities to specific audiences. The communication activities will be customized for 6 target audiences (TAs). Each audience is targeted to achieve at least one of the goals listed above. The 6 TAs are as follows:

- **Industry** (TA1): Building and construction professionals, coatings and chemical material producers, bio-based material producers, materials engineering firms, architecture and design studios, bio-waste producers, biotech industry, and technology providers.
- **Facility management professionals** (TA2): Those responsible for operation and maintenance, performance and quality, sustainability, and real estate.
- **Academia** (TA3): Experts, researchers, and professors in construction material technologies, civil engineering, biologists, chemists, physicists, and architects, both locally and globally.
- **Public entities** (TA4): Policymakers, national and sub-national ministerial advisors, civil servants in relevant ministries, authorities, official advisory bodies, responsible officials in EU institutions and relevant EU agencies, political advisors to national and EU elected policymakers, policy directors influencing public, private, and civil society sectors at international and national levels, relevant ‘think tanks’, and decisionmakers, inter-governmental organizations.
- **Journalists** (TA5): Local, regional, and international media outlets.
- **Society** (TA6): General public of different ages, genders, and socio-economic statuses; private consumers, citizen organizations, and environmental NGOs.

Table 1. REMEDY target audience aligned with communication objectives

Communication objective	Target audience
O1	Academia, Journalists, Society
O2	Industry, Academia, Public entities
O3	Industry, Facility management, Public entities, Society
O4	Industry, Facility management, Academia, Society
O5	Industry, Facility management, Academia, Public entities, Society
O6	Academia, Public entities, Journalists

REMEDY has identified key organizations and potential representatives from each target audience, focusing on decision-makers and multipliers who can facilitate the uptake and amplification of innovations relevant to the project.

- TA1: **Holcim**, **Saint-Gobain** (leading companies in sustainable construction), **Knauf Insulation** (makes insulation and building materials, commitment to sustainable and bio-based materials), **BASF** (develops biobased polymers and construction chemicals), **DuPont** (develops durable construction materials and digital inks), **Oxman** (design company fusing biology with technology).
- TA2: **European Facility Management (FM) network** (connects numerous facility managers across countries and is focused on EU climate initiatives such as Green Deal and similar), **Skanska group** (devoted to sustainable green buildings), **CBRE** (large-scale facility and asset management), **21stFM** (offers networking and tender opportunities).
- TA3: **Technical University of Munich** (departments focused on sustainable and bio-based materials, material engineering), **University of Ljubljana** (REMEDY partner, working with living microorganism important for ELMs), **ETH Zurich** (excellent research institution, has programs working on ELMs), **Engineered Living Materials Institute** (research organization dedicated to ELM research), **MIT Media Lab** (working on biofabrications and ELMs), **Leibniz Institute for New Materials** (focusing on development innovative materials, including ELMs).
- TA4: **EC Directorate-General for Environment** (sets EU environmental standards), **EC Directorate-General for Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs**, **DG GROW** (develops industrial policy on bio-based materials), **EIC** (funding mechanism, pathway for market), **Technology Council for Advanced Materials** (high-level group with representatives from the EU Member States, academia, industry, and other key players in research and innovation aiming to foster dialogue and collaboration to strengthen Europe's advanced materials sector, REMEDY coordinator is representing academia).
- TA5: **Slovenian Press Agency (STA)**, **Megafon**, **Regional obala**, **Primorske novice**, **Zelena Slovenija** (local media to reach general public); **Bio Engineer**, **Interesting Engineering**, **Science**, **Deutschlandfunk** (international media for a broader audience), **Dezeen** (architecture and design magazine), **ArchiDaily** (world's largest architectural platform).
- TA6: **Diverse stakeholders** at dedicated events, for example, European Researchers Night or NEB festival, engaged through various networks e.g., **Fab Lab Network** (open, creative community of fabricators, artists, scientists, engineers, educators, students, amateurs, professionals), **EIT Climate KIC** (leading, independent climate innovation agency and community).

Additionally, REMEDY identified specific communication and dissemination activities with which we will target the specific target audience (presented in tables 7 and 8 in the section Planned activities).

Communications messages

In line with the main goals of the project and the communication activities, six key communication messages (CMs) were developed to support the defined communication objectives. Each message is tailored to a defined target audience and will be disseminated through appropriate communication channels. The defined messages aim to translate the project’s scientific and technological developments into language that is appropriate for each target audience and will foster engagement, understanding, and maximize the project’s visibility.

Table 2. REMEDY communication messages aligned with the target audiences

Target audience	Key message
TA1 - Industry	CM1: REMEDY is developing breakthrough living inks as an alternative and sustainable technology for façade protection, decoration, and functionalization (O2, O3, O4, O5).
TA2 - Facility management	CM2: REMEDY inks offer multifunctionality and ensure long-lasting performance due to the presence of living cells and self-healing capacity (O3, O4, O5).
TA3 - Academia	CM3: ELMs in the form of living inks have the potential to revolutionize conventional materials design and REMEDY pioneers solutions that combine biology, ELMs and architecture (O1, O2, O4, O5, O6).
TA4 - Public entities	CM4: REMEDY supports the sustainable transition by developing a beneficial archibiome, introducing metabolic thinking in the circular building industry, and boosting probiotic architecture (O2, O3, O5, O6).
TA5 - Journalists	CM5: REMEDY is kicking off a microbial revolution in architecture, aiming to shift the negative public perception of microorganisms in architecture and turn buildings into living systems (O1, O6).
TA 6 - Society	CM6: REMEDY brings nature into cities by introducing beneficial microbiomes to create buildings that support human health and wellbeing (O1, O3, O4, O5).

Communications channels

To effectively reach REMEDY’s defined target audiences and ensure wide visibility and impact, the project will utilize several communication channels. These channels were selected to align effectively with the target audiences and are aligned with the overall communication objectives. The main communication channels used in the project are:

- **Website:** A dedicated section on the REMEDY website, including news, activities, updates, and results.

- **Social media:** A LinkedIn account was created for REMEDY, and social media accounts of all partner organizations will be used to share content about regular updates and achieved results.
- **Newsletter:** Published on the website and shared with interested stakeholders to inform them about the project progress, event invitations, and results highlights.
- **Press & media outreach:** Press releases and promotional content (professional articles) shared with local and international media outlets.
- **Video content:** Presentation of technology, interviews, case study, and sharing project results.
- **International events** (participation and organization): Attending local and international events (conferences, workshops, fairs, trainings, webinars, invited lectures) to present project activities and results, and organizing the final project event to present results.
- **Scientific publications:** Scientific papers in open-access journals will be prepared and published about project results to the academic and research communities.
- **Established platforms** – New European Bauhaus Academy Pioneer Hub: In-person and online trainings, micro credentials, co-creation workshops, educational sessions for young researchers, and contribution to lifelong learning.

On each channel, multiple communication messages can be shared and repeated to reinforce the effect. However, messages should be slightly adapted to be relevant for the channel and audience. Table 3 presents the primary messages that will be shared on each channel.

Table 3. REMEDY communication channels, aligned with target audiences and messages

Communication channel	Target audience	Key message
Website	TA1, TA3, TA6	CM1, CM3, CM6
Social media	TA5, TA6, TA3	CM5, CM6
Newsletter	TA1, TA2, TA3, TA4, TA6	CM1, CM2
Press & media outreach	TA4, TA5, TA6	CM4, CM5
Video content	TA1, TA3, TA4, TA6	CM2, CM6
International events	TA1, TA2, TA3, TA4	CM3, CM4
Scientific publication	TA3	CM1, CM3
Established platforms – New European Bauhaus Academy Pioneer Hub	TA1, TA3, TA4	CM4

Planned activities

The following planned activities will be implemented throughout the project's duration, leveraging multiple communication channels to maximize outreach and impact.

Table 4. REMEDY planned activities

Communication channel	Planned activity
Website	Regular updates, news articles, and results
Social media	Regular posts and updates
Newsletter	Reporting project achievements
Press & media outreach	Press releases, promotional content, presenting project objectives to society
Video content	Presentation of technology, interviews, case studies
International events	Attending and organizing events, presentations, panels, presenting the final results, sharing project progress and results, co-creation with NEB network
Scientific publication	Publishing scientific papers in open open-access journals
Established platforms – New European Bauhaus Academy Pioneer Hub	Training materials, co-creation sessions, and micro-credentials

In Tables 5 and 6, we present the proposed timeline for planned dissemination and communication activities divided into years (Y1-Y4) and quarters (Q1-Q4).

Table 5. Timeline of dissemination activities

Activity	Timeline
Participation in events (conferences, fairs)	Y1, Q3 – Y4-Q4
European Researchers' Night & outreach events	Y1, Q4; Y2, Q4; Y3, Q4; Y4, Q4
Contribution to ELMs Portfolio activities	Y1, Q1 – Y4-Q4
Scientific publications	Y1, Q2; Y1, Q4; Y2, Q1; Y2, Q4; Y3, Q1; Y3, Q4; Y4, Q1; Y4, Q4
NEB training curricula	Y4-Q4

Table 6: Timeline of communication activities

Activity	Timeline
Communication strategy setup & alignment	Y1, Q1
Website launch & regular updates	Y1, Q2 – Y4-Q4

Social media setup & engagement	Y1, Q2 – Y4-Q4
Visual identity & branding materials	Y1, Q1 - Y1, Q2
Press releases / project updates / newsletters	Y1, Q2; Y1, Q4; Y2, Q2; Y2, Q4; Y3, Q2; Y3, Q4; Y4, Q2; Y4, Q4
Videos, infographics & storytelling	Y1, Q3; Y2, Q1; Y2, Q3; Y3, Q1; Y3, Q3; Y4, Q1; Y4, Q3
Final dissemination campaign & results report	Y1, Q2– Y4-Q4

Additionally, we list a roadmap for relevant events that REMEDY partners will consider attending and/or organizing with the aim of enhancing the project’s visibility and supporting wider dissemination and uptake of REMEDY activities and results.

- ELSA Summer School on Engineered Living Materials 2026
- World Cities Day 2026
- Next-Gen Materials & Engineering 2026
- EIC Summit 2026
- ILASS Europe 2026 (34th European Meeting on Liquid Atomization and Spray Systems)
- FUN-EX 2026 (Second International Conference on Extremophilic Fungi)
- SETCOMS 2026 & MIKROMED REGIO 6 (1st South-East Transnational Congress on Microbial Sciences)
- BiofilmsON’2026 (6th Practical Course & Symposium on Biofilms)
- BPP 2026 (Biopartitioning and Purification Conference 2026)
- SWMMS 2026 (Sustainable Waste Management in Materials Science)
- Regulatory Readiness for emerging biotechnology solutions through the lens of Engineered Living Materials (30 April 2026)
- REMEDY final event

More conferences and events will be continuously identified, assessed, considered, and confirmed as the project progresses and evolves.

Moreover, we list below the planned communication and dissemination activities related to the identified REMEDY target audience to ensure comprehensive reach.

Table 7: Planned dissemination activities

Dissemination activity	TA	Why?	Who contributes?
Participation in events (conferences, fairs)	TA1, TA2, TA3, TA4	To establish ties and network with relevant stakeholders.	All partners
European Researchers’ Night & outreach events	TA2, TA3, TA4, TA5, TA6	To raise public awareness, engage with students and the society.	All partners

Contribution to ELMs Portfolio activities	TA4	To enhance impact via portfolio, influence policy at EU level, connect with relevant projects.	All partners
Scientific publications	TA3	Advance knowledge in the field, provide evidence and showcase scientific innovation.	All partners
NEB training curricula	TA1, TA3, TA4	To support transition by developing training content related to scientific and technological REMEDY innovations.	All partners

Table 8: Planned communication activities

Communication activity	TA	Why?	Who contributes?
Website	TA1, TA3, TA6	Central hub for REMEDY to raise awareness, showcase results, highlight activities, promote new knowledge and engage stakeholders.	UP leads, other partners contribute
Social media	TA1-TA6	Raise awareness, engage stakeholders, community building.	UP leads, other partners contribute
Newsletter	TA1, TA2, TA3, TA4, TA6	Direct reach, raise awareness and engage stakeholders.	UP leads, other partners contribute
Press & media outreach	TA4, TA5, TA6	Raise awareness, showcase results, highlight activities, promote new knowledge and policy relevance.	UP leads, other partners contribute
Video content	TA1, TA3, TA4, TA6	High engagement, visual explanation.	UP leads, other partners contribute
Final dissemination campaign & results report	TA1-TA6	Showcase results, activities, new knowledge, innovations, and engage stakeholders.	UP leads, other partners contribute

Monitoring and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

Regular monitoring of dissemination activities will be conducted to evaluate and measure the impacts of each action/activity. The KPIs – which are developed according to SMART (specific, measurable, achievable, relevant and time-bound) principles – in the table below present the number that will be achieved during the whole duration of the project.

Table 9. REMEDY KPIs of planned activities

Communication channel	Planned activity	KPI
Website	Regular updates, news articles, results	Number of views (> 5000 views)
Social media	Regular posts and updates	Number of posts (monthly posts, at least 48 posts)
Newsletter	Reporting on project achievements	Number of sent newsletters (at least 2 newsletters per year)
Press & media outreach	Press releases, promotional content, present project objectives to society	Number of press releases sent (at least 4)
Video content	Presentation of technology, interviews, case study	Number of views (> 70 views)
International events	Presentation, panel, present the final results, present project progress and results, co-create with NEB network	Number of participants at organized final event (> 100 participants), attending > 15 conferences, > 3 workshops, > 3 training, 4 webinars, > 5 fairs
Scientific publication	Publishing scientific papers in open open-access journals	Number of papers published (> 25 papers)
Established platforms – New European Bauhaus Academy Pioneer Hub	Training materials, co-creation sessions, micro-credentials	Number of curriculums (1 for > 100 professionals)

Additionally, we will measure:

- Number of posted news articles on the website;
- Number of engagements on social media (likes, shares, comments, and post reach related to REMEDY).

In addition to monitoring quantitative KPIs, the REMEDY communication and dissemination strategy will incorporate qualitative evaluation methods to assess the broader impact and effectiveness of its outreach efforts. Feedback mechanisms will include structured surveys distributed to stakeholders, event participants, and target audiences to gather insights on message clarity, relevance, and engagement. Possible focus groups and interviews with key stakeholders, such as researchers, industry partners, and policy influencers, could be conducted to collect more nuanced feedback on communication materials and activities. Social media engagement metrics and sentiment analysis will also be used to estimate public perception and response. These qualitative assessments will inform ongoing adjustments to the strategy, ensuring that communication remains responsive, inclusive, and aligned with the needs and expectations of diverse audience groups.

The dissemination activities will also be monitored with the help of a shared Excel file where all partners will record their dissemination and communication activities. The common file was prepared by UP and each partner is responsible for reporting activities in the shared document.

The WP7 leader is responsible for tracking and reviewing the document monthly, sending reminders and requesting clarification, if needed.

Supporting materials

To support all the listed activities, the REMEDY visual identity and project branding were developed at the beginning of the project. This includes:

- Developed and designed MS Word and PowerPoint templates;
- Developed and designed the REMEDY project logo, including usage guidelines;
- Developed and designed typographic elements;
- Developed and designed the REMEDY project website;
- Created a social media account on LinkedIn.

Additionally, project flyers will be created to communicate technological progress developed in REMEDY.

All partners are expected to use the REMEDY logo and templates in public presentations, event materials, and publications to ensure consistent project branding.

Alignment with ELM's portfolio communication strategy

The REMEDY communication and dissemination strategy will be fully aligned with the overarching EIC ELMs Portfolio communication framework to ensure coherence, amplify impact, and enhance shared opportunities. By adhering to the ELMs Communication Guidelines developed by the Communication Working Group, REMEDY will contribute to a unified representation of the Portfolio and support joint outreach efforts aimed at raising public awareness, engaging stakeholders, and promoting the societal benefits of Engineered Living Materials. REMEDY will adopt the Portfolio's key messages, target audience segmentation, and best practices, particularly in engaging citizens, researchers, and relevant industry communities, while retaining flexibility to address project-specific goals. Participation in shared initiatives such as the Horizon Results Booster and public outreach events like the European Researchers' Night will further ensure that REMEDY's communication efforts are synergistic with the collective goals of the ELMs portfolio.

Crisis communication

While REMEDY aims to promote the societal acceptance of microbial biofilm in architecture, we recognize that innovative concepts such as "living coatings" or microbial-based materials may be misinterpreted by the public, media, or other stakeholders. In rare cases, misunderstandings or misinformation could lead to reputational risks or negatively affect public perception.

To address such scenarios, REMEDY will implement a basic crisis communication protocol, in line with the principles of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), supporting transparency, trust, and societal engagement.

- **Monitoring:** The project will regularly check media coverage and social media activity to spot any misunderstandings or negative reactions.
- **Response coordination:** If a risk to the project's reputation is identified, the coordinator and WP7 leader will gather a team of partner representatives to agree to a response.
- **Messaging:** The response will be clear, accurate, and aligned with EU values. It will be adapted to suit the specific audience and platform.
- **Escalation:** If needed, the team may contact communication experts or EU advisory bodies for support.

Responsibilities

UP coordinates all communication efforts and coordinates activities. The WP7 leader is responsible for day-to-day coordination, website, social media content, newsletter preparation and other related activities. UP also takes care that the interface with Exploitation activities is performed. Other project partners collaborate closely, review and suggest developed activities, and share communication efforts on their channels.

REMEDY

BUILDING TOMORROW WITH LIVING ARCHITECTURE

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